

Sars-CoV-2 multi-systemic inflammatory syndrome in children and adolescents (MIS-C)

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Abstract

Multi-systemic inflammatory syndrome in children (MIS-C), which can develop for as yet unclear reasons following an infection with SARS-CoV-2, occurs even in the absence of a COVID-19 disease (infection without symptoms) prior to its onset. The complication is a fatal risk, especially for adolescents, according to a recent US study.¹

Discussion

The belief (or myth) that Sars-CoV-2 cannot harm children and adolescents is wrong. This important information has finally reached the scientific community. It was to be expected, however, considering that hCoV virus NL63 (a kind of cousin of Sars-CoV-2) is notoriously known to also damage the endothelium and to cause a Kawasaki syndrome-like clinical condition in children. This demonstrates once again that the neglect of corona virus research is now taking its revenge. Because in many aspects, the clinical picture we all now call Covid-19 resembles a mixture of the symptoms of hCoV NL63 and OC43, albeit with a more severe symptomatology. In the United States at least 2,000 children and adolescents have contracted the post-Covid MIS syndrome since the Wuhan virus caused a pandemic. That the illness, first described in the United Kingdom, is indeed caused by SARS-CoV-2 is now beyond all doubt. The MIS-C (C = children) followed the COVID-19 wave in all parts of the United States of America at intervals of up to 5 weeks, confirming the pathogenetic concepts. Researchers speculate that MIS-C is not directly caused by Sars-CoV-2. Rather, there appears to be a connection with the immune response to the pathogen. This is supported by the fact that the onset of the disease often coincides with the peak of antibody production and that patients produce particularly large numbers of antibodies against the receptor binding site of SARS-CoV-2. What is more, similar syndromes with a shorter or longer latency period are known, for example after a measles disease or in the case of PANS syndrome. The US-patients hospitalized with MIS-C showed a strong inflammatory reaction, which does not match the mild and asymptomatic course of infection with SARS-2. CRP and interleukin-6 were several times above the reference values. In addition, CDC researchers found thrombocytopenia in 40% and lymphopenia in 31% of the MIS-C patients.^{1,4,6}

However, a previous COVID-19 disease was documented in only one quarter of the MIS-C patients under 16 years of age.¹

In just 52%, an infection had been previously documented with a common PCR test. In 83% seroconversion with a detection of antibodies against SARS-CoV-2 had occurred at the onset of MIS-C. In most patients MIS-C began suddenly. The illness typically started highly acute with high fever that persisted up to 7 days or more in the US patients. This was usually accompanied by abdominal pain (77%), nausea (82%), a rash (58%), diarrhea (55%), and hyperemia in the conjunctivae (42%). Respiratory symptoms such as cough, dyspnea, and chest pain were reported in less than 40% of patients. Unstable blood pressure occurred in 55% of patients. Cardiac dysfunction was documented in 34%, myocarditis in 20%, and coronary artery dilation or aneurysms in 18% of patients. Coronary artery aneurysms are among the most feared long-term sequelae of Kawasaki syndrome (one form of it caused by corona-virus NL63). However, there are also differences, which is why MIS is now considered a separate clinical entity. But this not too relevant for the patients. On a meta-level all these viruses and syndromes are associated with processes in walls of the blood-vessels. The fact that MIS-C is indeed a severe clinical condition is proven by the fact that at least 4 organ systems were affected in 92% of the children. More than half of the children (60%) had to be treated in an intensive care unit (ICU). Although lethality was

“only” 1.4% it increased with patient age to 3% in 15- to 17-year-olds and to 12% in 18- to 20-year-olds. Treatment of MIS, similar to Kawasaki syndrome, is with intravenous immunoglobulins. Intravenous immunoglobulins are widely used. However, the efficacy or dangers of intravenous immunoglobulins have not yet been proven in MIS-C, unlike in Kawasaki syndrome. A total of 71% were treated with steroids according to the US-study. However, whether steroids improve prognosis in MIS-C has also not yet been proven.¹⁻⁶

Conclusions

Children and adolescents should get access to Sars-CoV-2 mRNA vaccines (and only to those) as soon as possible.

Acknowledgements

We thank all individuals who were willing to volunteer for this paper and CERN for their always very helpful support.

Source of funding and conflicts of interest

No external funding.

No conflicts of interest.

Ethical standards, data safety compliance and patient’s rights

This article is about scientific facts. It is not reporting on a clinical trial (or anything similar) in its legal definition, especially not a prospective one. Our work was conducted in accordance with the Declaration of Helsinki.

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